

SCIENTIFIC AND PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF THE USE OF DIDACTIC MATERIAL IN THE FORMATION OF EDUCATIONAL EDUCATION AT SCHOOL

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Abstract

The article considers the scientific and pedagogical basis for the use of didactic material in plant growing lessons and the role of didactic games in the aesthetic education of future young professionals in the formation of educational education at school, used didactic materials and directions and types of games in plant growing lessons. These basic scientific ideas are abstract in nature, so scientists use different models to explain them.

Keywords: didactic material, didactic games, scientific ideas, education, aesthetic education.

Currently, in the era of universal globalization and the rapid development of the flow of information, Higher Education has the goal of training young personnel at a globally competitive level. To this end, the development of comprehensive professional knowledge of future specialists is an urgent issue.

4 Messages of the Head of State N.A.Nazarbayev "Strategy"Kazakhstan-2050" new political course of the established state " " Education and professional skills - the main guidelines of the modern system of education, training and retraining of personnel"- "to become a competitive developed state, we must become a country with high literacy.When in the modern world it has become not enough just mass literacy.Our citizens should be ready to constantly master the skills of working on the most advanced equipment and in the most modern production.It is also necessary to pay great attention to the functional literacy of our children, in general, the entire teenage generation.It is very important for our children to be adapted to modernity"[1]- special attention is paid to comprehensive literacy and knowledge, qualifications of young people and future specialists.In this context, one of the urgent problems is the formation of professional orientation of students.

Living natural objects in the discipline of crop production and their types. Planting of indoor plants, decoration . Taking care of them.Decoration of flowers from garden plants.

Natural visual aids for the course of plant growing are specially selected indoor plants, plants obtained from a training experimental site or brought from a reservoir, on a cape of wildlife, in an aquarium, a terrarium.

In order for students to clearly and deeply assimilate the course of plant growing, they need to be given a comprehensive understanding of the objects and phenomena of the plant world, for which in the learning process the main attention is paid to the first source of knowledge – the

direct vision of wildlife, which is carried out by visual study of the lesson. It is not difficult to provide each lesson of plant growing with live and specially developed natural materials, since it is practically easy to collect, prepare, store, and every school can afford it.

Not only for demonstration of natural remedies in the lesson, but also for the work of students, i.e. for distribution to students in a laboratory lesson. The teacher should always remember the need to give a plant to each student. Direct control over living objects, work with them, experimentation ensure the formation of a complete and clear understanding among students, which is one of the most important educational tasks facing the school course of botany.

Natural objects are used in plant growing lessons, as a rule, in combination with the means of other groups, since only in such conditions are the most favorable conditions created for students to study the laws of the external and internal structure and vital activity of various plants, their systematics. After all, each type of visual aid has its own didactic capabilities that increase cognitive activity and motivation of students. Therefore, the circumstance that is taken into account when choosing visual aids in a particular lesson: to perform tasks, it is necessary to use various visual aids pedagogically correctly, depending on the purpose, task and material of a particular lesson [2].

The provision of plant growing classes with the necessary educational equipment depends, first of all, on the initiative and activity of the teacher himself. Visual aids necessary for teaching the subject of crop production, the teacher systematically collects annually, prepares visual aids from them. Taking into account the fact that the preparation of materials for demonstration in the classroom and distribution to students depends on the season, the teacher draws up a calendar plan for collecting plants and developing visual aids from them, contains materials contained in the plan in natural conditions, on the site of the practice school, in the fields of agriculture, as well as by stages and phases of development and materials obtained as a result of experiments with objects sorted at separate stages are also taken into account materials obtained as a result of students' experiments, practical work, experiments with objects sorted by individual stages and stages of plant development and growth. Students collect a lot of interesting material from places where they were in the summer. The teacher selects their needs for the lesson.

The object will look like a list, each object should be divided according to the deadlines for collecting handouts, the task given to individual students, etc. In each handout, in addition to the name of the object, the conditions and terms of its manufacture, the requirements for storage, care, preparation and operation for the corresponding lesson are specified. Gradually, a complete handout is being created, reflecting all the material necessary for teaching botany [3]. Visual aids should be organized by students under the direct supervision of the teacher. The adjustment of natural materials is most often performed by students united in a circle of young naturalists, or a special circle for the development of visual aids. Wildlife materials include plant seeds, fruits, the surface of the Earth, underground parts, the use of a single path to school, or wild or cultivated plants that can lead to the long-term preservation of some of them.

The general didactic step towards learning tools is considered in the research of V. V. Kraevsky et al. [4].

However, the creation and application of learning tools based on accumulated experience is not a guarantee of achieving high results in teaching biology. This is evidenced by the following.

Firstly, the diverse classification of teaching aids and the lack of known principles.

Secondly, the orientation of modern pedagogy in the educational process, the determination on its basis of the technological step and the purpose of learning through the content of the discipline, the process of activity of the teacher or student, all this does not allow to determine a certain learning outcome.

Systematic study of learning tools in this way, and an opinion about them, as an element of learning technology, allows participants to form their own knowledge.

This step will improve the educational process, increase the possibilities of using didactic materials.

Methodological science is rich in its experience in how it can be used in practice. The main problem of the methodology is the problem of using didactic material in teaching biology.

Despite the accumulated experience, many questions were asked about the use of didactic materials, and we believe that their solution is related to:

- the place of didactic material in the learning system and the role of use in the educational process;

- considers the value of didactic materials as an element of learning technology, in the context of personality-oriented learning of independent cognition.

Literature as a didactic handout does not sufficiently reveal the essence of this type of didactic material. Although didactic handouts on various sections of biology are deeply debated issues, they conduct training activities to study objects and phenomena of nature (places of work). The didactic material is sufficiently developed to be able to combine the structure and management of this activity of the organization. This opportunity is a particularly relevant didactic handout in the context of the implementation of a technological approach to student-oriented learning. It consists in the formation in this case of a more effective use of new educational material, its consolidation, correction or verification as the main manifestation of the mobility of the learning process and various educational and methodological handouts.

The analysis of scientific, educational and methodological literature on the design and use of teaching materials revealed the lack of sufficiently clear and precise requirements for these types of textbooks.

Surveys of teachers of secondary educational institutions in Turkestan have shown that the degree of use of educational and methodological materials for teaching biology is insufficient. Despite the fact that teaching materials are widely used by teachers in practice, they mainly use didactic materials to control students' knowledge.

Most often, teachers use didactic materials to familiarize themselves with the object they have passed for the first time, and instead of glass, living objects, they use them to familiarize themselves with natural phenomena. These phenomena determine that much attention should be paid to the problem of the methodology of using didactic material for teaching biology.

The object of our research was a student and a teacher. Only when they turned out to be a close educational and cognitive activity, our research turned out to be successful and effective.

The study and generalizing analysis of psychological, pedagogical, methodological and special literature allowed us in the following cases: the use of the methodology of teaching

materials will be improved if the usefulness of didactic materials, which are the effectiveness of teaching, is increased:

- it will be aimed at independently strengthening the cognitive activity of students;
- be focused on the implementation of technological approaches to the use of complex ideas and didactic means of student-oriented learning;
- Include the use of educational and methodological materials developed taking into account psychological, pedagogical, physiological and other requirements;

In our study, we found that didactic games in the lessons of plant growing can also be used in the process of explaining a new topic, repetition, practice, exercises. In addition to the development of thinking and improving the thinking of students, games have a great impact on the conscious and firm assimilation of the studied, passed topics.

The game gives correct results only when in close contact with the content of educational subjects. The technology of game learning is widely used in the lessons of crop production.

Currently, the problem of play occupies a significant place in a number of large-scale studies, determining its importance in the development of a child. With the help of didactic games, the education of students on the foundations of world virtue and decency was started. To do this, it is necessary to effectively use advanced models of world education, proven sources of education in the process of teaching biology. In this direction:

1. ideological, political, moral and aesthetic education;
2. forming the right attitude to the world;
3. to foster respect for the rich, artistic, respect and love for the country, the land of our homeland.;
4. to improve the acquired knowledge and reading skills, skills, develop the language;
5. it is necessary to cultivate an interest in work, diligence.

Therefore, it is necessary to base didactic, game lessons on comprehensive education of students in the lessons of plant growing. In this regard, the work on mastering crop production through didactic games should have the following goals:

- a) the widespread use of didactic games in combination with sources of learning through games in teaching botanical riddles, surveys, crosswords;
- b) formation of students' correct attitude to culture and literature by transmitting works of art in the form of a didactic game;
- c) with the help of didactic games, it is necessary to teach students eloquence and form their biological language.

The didactic game evening is one of the educational works, which is very exciting in emotional terms. The conducted didactic game evenings have a great influence on the interest of not only listeners, viewers, but also participants.

That is, in the process of applying the didactic game in the lessons of plant growing, we identified the following values:

- With the help of game elements, with the help of increasing, achieving results when working in a team;

- Independent search for students for creative work develops the skills of curiosity, interest in knowledge;

- To be able to protect your body from the nature of the environment of the younger generation

educates

So, in the course of the study, the following conclusions were made:

- developed places of application of didactic material in the educational process, steps for its formation and use;

- the rationale for the use of didactic material has been developed from the point of view of the use of didactic tools in the curriculum, the implementation of complex and technological approaches;

- clarified the requirements for didactic materials;

- methods of using teaching material in teaching scientific biology have been developed and improved.

References

1. "Qazshstan-2050" Strategiysy qalypqtaskan memekettei zhaңa sayasi bayyty // Ontustyk Qazahstan.-2012, Zheltoksan - 15.- №198-199.-p.8.
2. Isayev I.I., Khalikova GS, Alpamysova G.B. Biology of Oyytuədisteme.- Shymkent, Əlembaspasy, 2017. p. 556.
3. Begaliev RN, Isaev F.I., ErgubekovaZh.S. Okutudininnovasialikaspetileri. -Shymkent, Əlembaspasy, 2017. p. 112.
4. Didactics of secondary school: Some problems of modern didactics. V. Krayevsky, I. I. Lerner; Ed. MN Skatkina. The 2nd edition is augmented and revised. -M .: Education, 2002. p. 319.